

Diversity Analysis of a Quinoa (*Chenopodium quinoa* Willd.) Germplasm during Two Seasons

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Abstract : The present work has been carried out to evaluate the diversity of a collection of 78 quinoa accessions developed through recurrent selection from Andean germplasm introduced to Morocco in the winter of 2000. Twenty-three quantitative and qualitative characters were used for the evaluation of genetic diversity and the relationship between the accessions, and also for the establishment of a core collection in Morocco. Important variation was found among the accessions in terms of plant morphology and growth behavior. Data analysis showed positive correlation of the plant height, the plant fresh and the dry weight with the grain yield, while days to flowering was found to be negatively correlated with grain yield. The first four PCs contributed 74.76 % of the variability; the first PC showed significant variation with 42.86 % of the total variation, PC2 with 15.37 %, PC3 with 9.05 % and PC4 contributed 7.49% of the total variation. Plant size, days to grain filling and days to maturity are correlated to the PC1; and seed size, inflorescence density and mildew resistance are correlated to the PC2. Hierarchical cluster analysis rearranged the 78 quinoa accessions into four main groups and ten sub-clusters. Clustering was found in associations with days to maturity and also with plant size and seed-size traits

Keywords : Character association, *Chenopodium quinoa*, Diversity analysis, Morphotypic cluster, Multivariate analysis.

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